

Table S5. Reproductive modes of the species included

Species	Aquatic/terrestrial/direct
<i>Adenomera andreae</i>	Terrestrial
<i>Adenomera heyeri</i>	Terrestrial
<i>Adenomera hylaedactyla</i>	Terrestrial
<i>Adenomera marmorata</i>	Terrestrial
<i>Adenomera saci</i>	Terrestrial
<i>Adenomera simonstuarti</i>	Terrestrial
<i>Adenomera thomei</i>	Terrestrial
<i>Allobates femoralis</i>	Terrestrial
<i>Allobates nidicola</i>	Terrestrial
<i>Allobates paleovarzensis</i>	Terrestrial
<i>Ameerega hahneli</i>	Direct
<i>Ameerega trivittata</i>	Direct
<i>Anomaloglossus baeobatrachus</i>	Terrestrial
<i>Anomaloglossus stepheni</i>	Terrestrial
<i>Atelopus franciscus</i>	Aquatic
<i>Rhinella abei</i>	Aquatic
<i>Rhinella ornata</i>	Aquatic
<i>Craugastor podiciferus</i>	Direct
<i>Craugastor talamancae</i>	Direct
<i>Dendropsophus ebraccatus</i>	Aquatic
<i>Dendropsophus minutus 2</i>	Aquatic
<i>Dendropsophus minutus 36</i>	Aquatic
<i>Dendropsophus minutus 39</i>	Aquatic
<i>Dendropsophus minutus 40</i>	Aquatic
<i>Dendropsophus minutus 42</i>	Aquatic
<i>Dendropsophus leucophyllatus</i>	Aquatic
<i>Ranitomeya ventrimaculata</i>	Terrestrial
<i>Adenomera diptyx</i>	Terrestrial
<i>Engystomops petersi</i>	Terrestrial
<i>Hypsiboas andinus</i>	Aquatic
<i>Hypsiboas aff semilineatus</i>	Aquatic
<i>Leptodactylus fuscus</i>	Terrestrial
<i>Leptodactylus mystaceus</i>	Terrestrial
<i>Engystomops pustulosus</i>	Terrestrial
<i>Pristimantis chiastonotus</i>	Direct
<i>Pristimantis ridens</i>	Direct
<i>Pristimantis zeucotylus</i>	Direct
<i>Rhinella martyi</i>	Aquatic